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Forensic Linguistic Investigation of Trademark Infringement in Pakistan: An Ortho-Semiotic analysis of food and Cosmetic Products

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Abstract: *This research conducts a forensic linguistic investigation of trademarks of consumer products, specifically food and cosmetic products, in Pakistan to pinpoint linguistic infringement patterns including orthography and visual semiotics. This study takes its theoretical background from the work of Olsson (2008) who notes that linguistic tools and techniques help explore forensic texts involved in criminal activity. Remotely collected photographs of food and cosmetic products with similar trademarks sold in local markets of Pakistan are used as data in this study. This data was analyzed through the Ortho-Semiotic Forensic Linguistic Analysis method, a proposed model resulting from model triangulation process. This model is put into words by combining relative linguistic features from two linguistic analysis models of trademark infringement proposed by Shuy (2002) and Butters (2008). Findings reveal that language plays a prominent role in trademark infringement, which eventually has become the reason for 'likelihood of confusion' found among trademarks. This likelihood of confusion is caused mainly by the use of similar orthography, visual semiotic features (color, design and style), pronunciation, stress patterns of syllables, morphemic count, morphemic order and positioning that are used to deceive customers. Additionally, this research offers a comprehensive forensic linguistic analysis of trademark infringement with the aim to contribute to the collection of courtroom evidence for the jury and for suspects to defend themselves from allegations of guilt. A more in-depth exploration of other features of language, such as semantic and pragmatic knowledge, is recommended for future research in the field of trademark infringement in Pakistan.*

Keywords: Trademarks, Trademark infringement, Trademark infringement in Pakistan, Forensic linguistics, Likelihood of confusion, Ortho-semiotic forensic linguistic approach

1. INTRODUCTION

A mark or trademark is an essential element of business and trade market. 3,500 years ago, archaeologists observed that potters used to draw marks on their products to distinguish them from the work of other potters (Shuy, 2002). Over time, these marks transformed into different shapes (with either semiotic or orthographic features) and now have not only a specific criterion for their formation but also a legal system to protect them from infringement (Adams, 2002). These marks are called trademarks and are defined as registered words, phrases, and images used in trade and business markets to differentiate among freely accessible goods and services from one another so they cannot be used by anyone without permission (Walter, 2008). In short, "they are the products of linguistic and semiotic language which are owned by people, organizations and institutions" (Coulthard et al., 2020, p. 352).

Butters (2008) views 'trademark' as an umbrella term encompassing different aspects of proprietary trade names and marks such as service marks (trademarks used for services), proprietary slogans (phrases used for advertisement), logos (trademark symbols), and designs (visual style of products) (p. 231). Millot (2009) opines that trademarks are symbols of differentiation for customers because they are used to identify the original product in the market. Furthermore, trademarks help customers buy

desired products while avoiding unwanted items (Economides, 1998).

Counterfeit products infringe on original trademarks to dupe customers into buying fake products (Simonson, 1994). Trademark infringement deceives customers while harming original trademark owners. Howard, Kerin, and Gengler (2000) propose trademark infringement as the illegal use of the trademark of a company by another company without permission or consent of its trademark owner. "Infringement of trademark rights can occur when a mark is adopted that is the same or sufficiently similar to the mark of another and makes use of that mark for sufficiently related products or services" (Shuy, 2002, p. 30).

Legal processes of issues related to trademark infringement are studied in forensic linguistics (Olsson, 2008). As legal advisors, forensic linguists bring forth their knowledge and capability to tackle four main problems in this field:

'Likelihood of confusion' between two trademarks which look alike Labelling 'strength of a mark' regarding its semantic and pragmatic categories technically characterized as: 'generic, descriptive, suggestive, fanciful and arbitrary' 'Propriety of a mark' showing if it is 'scandalous or disparaging' Dilution of trademarks, a new area in need of further exploration (Butters, 2008)

Consents of forensic linguists are used as testimonials. They write descriptive reports about specific cases of trademark infringement based on their forensic linguistic analysis (Shuy, 2002). This research focuses on the problem of 'likelihood of confusion' to gather evidence on linguistic infringement patterns used by infringers.

In Pakistan, consumer products, especially in food and cosmetics categories, use different linguistic patterns of infringement. Consumer products are goods bought for daily routine use, categorized into three main kinds: consumer durable products, consumer non-durable products, and consumer services (Kolb, 2008). Consumer durable products are goods with a considerable life span of three or more years like household appliances, furniture, gadgets, and automobiles. Consumer non-durable products are goods with a short life span of minutes to years like food, beverages, and cosmetics (Kolb, 2008). Both are tangible while consumer services are intangible like facilities provided to customers in restaurants, repair shops, barber shops, beauty salons, and hotels (Kolb, 2008). Each product or service is distinguished by its specific logo or trademark in individual ownership of a company or service provider. For this study, trademarks of food and cosmetic products (consumer non-durable goods) are selected because they frequently face trademark infringement.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Trademarks differentiate among products of multiple companies. Trademark infringement occurs when the trademark of one company is illegally used by another company without the trademark owner's permission. Enforcement of trademark infringement laws in Pakistan is still under evolution within the legal policymaking research domain while there is little to no research from the forensic linguistic perspective in this field. Meanwhile, frequent cases of trademark infringements keep misleading the public into buying fake products with confusing linguistic patterns (along with orthographic and visual semiotic features). To understand these patterns, the present study focuses on linguistic elements exploited in trademark infringement in order to help customers buy original products and to help trademark owners provide evidence for suing counterfeit goods owners.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

- I. To identify linguistic infringement patterns from the perspective of orthography and visual semiotic features
- II. To identify linguistic infringement patterns from the perspective of phonetics and phonology
- III. To identify linguistic infringement patterns from the perspective of morphology

1.3 Research Questions

1. What are the linguistic infringement patterns from the perspective of orthography and visual semiotic language?
2. What are the linguistic infringement patterns from the perspective of phonetics and phonology?
3. What are the linguistic infringement patterns from the perspective of morphology?

1.4 Significance of the Study

This research will help customers identify infringement patterns while buying original products. It will provide evidence for courtroom decisions regarding trademark infringement cases in Pakistan. It will facilitate jury members in solving crimes related to trademark infringement by making accurate judgments. By giving a comprehensive forensic linguistic analysis of trademark infringement, it will help lawyers defend trademark owners and help suspects defend themselves from false allegations. Moreover, this research may suggest a proposed model for forensic linguistic analysis of trademarks in the Pakistani market to find linguistic infringement patterns.

1.5 Delimitations of the Study

This research is limited to a number of trademarks of food and cosmetic products from the Pakistani local market. The present study is geographically limited to the city of Peshawar, KP, Pakistan. Only food and cosmetic products are collected because they exhibit maximum likelihood of trademark infringement. Among all food and cosmetic products, only the alike trademark holders are collected from the internet as data for this research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Forensic Linguistics

Linguistics is the scientific study of features of language (Robins, 2014). Language is considered by a number of researchers who work in the context of law to investigate linguistic patterns involved in legal cases (Levi & Walker, 1990). Olsson (2008) defines forensic linguistics as a branch of applied linguistics that deals with the scientific study of language in the context of legal and forensic fields. He considers forensic linguistics as an 'interface between language, crime and law' where a forensic text (a text type that is associated with the legal and criminal context) is examined (Olsson, 2008). The work of a lawyer and a forensic linguist must not be confused as the former works to 'persuade or convince' jury members while the latter works to give an 'opinion or to explain that opinion' (Olsson, 2008).

Forensic Linguistics is a novel approach to applied linguistics (Li, 2011). It takes its instruments for legal and criminal investigations from other sub-disciplines of linguistics which may involve phonetics, phonology, semantics, pragmatics, stylistics, dialectology, and discourse studies (Ramezani, Sani, & Moghadam, 2016). Forensic linguistics is divided into sub-branches (McMenamin, 2002); some are directly linked to forensic linguistics like document examination in legal settings, software forensics, semiotics, authorship analysis, courtroom decisions, trademark litigation, and plagiarism detection, while some sub-branches are indirectly linked like psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, and literary forensics (McMenamin, 2002).

2.2 Trademarks and Trademark Infringement

Trademarks are defined as signs, words, logos, phrases, etc., used by firms to differentiate their status and products from other firms in the market (Millot, 2009). Trademarks distinguish distinct words or logos that become the manufacturers' identity (Economides, 1998). McCabe (2000) views trademarks

as a 'merchandising short-cut' because they are used for the ease of consumers to buy products which have satisfied them. Butters (2012) notes that trademark is a broader term used for firms (e.g., Hilal Food Limited in Pakistan), non-profit organizations (COMSATS University Islamabad), products (Hilal CupCake), services (Faisal Movers, Leopard Courier), names of products (CupKake, Fresh Up), slogans (Zong-'say it all'), or images (the logo of COMSATS University portrays a globe).

Shuy (2002) defines trademark infringement as: "Infringement of trademark rights can occur when a mark is adopted that is the same or sufficiently similar to the mark of another and makes use of that mark for sufficiently related products or services" (p. 30). Moreover, Butters (2012) defines trademark infringement as the adoption of other company trademarks as one's own for the purpose of confusing customers to:

- i. Damage the image of original trademark holder in the market by providing low standard products with the name of the original one
- ii. Get benefits from the owner's reputation in the market by selling low-standard products with a high name

2.3 Legal Aspects of Trademark Infringement

According to the Pakistan Trademark Ordinance 2001, a trademark is defined in Chapter 1, Section 2 as, "any mark capable of being represented graphically which is capable of distinguishing goods or services of one undertaking from those of other undertakings" (Ordinance, 2001, p. 5). Furthermore, a mark is defined as, "a device, brand, heading, label, ticket, name including person name, signature, word, letter, numeral, figurative elements, color, sound or/and combination thereof" (Ordinance, 2001, p. 4). Trademark infringement in Pakistan has been defined by Chapter 4, Section 40 of the Pakistan Trademark Ordinance 2001: trademark infringement occurs when a company produces 'identically and deceptively similar' products like the registered trademark owners. Such products are called 'counterfeit trademark goods' that are not registered and have the same description and are closely related to the original trademark (Ordinance, 2001).

2.4 Linguistic Aspect of Trademark Infringement and Models for Linguistic Analysis

Along with legal procedures, language plays a vital role in the trademark infringement process which is studied at the level of forensic linguistics. Olsson (2008) views forensic linguistics as a connection between language, crime, and law. Two prominent models have been proposed by Shuy (2002) and Butters (2008).

2.4.1 Shuy's Model of Linguistic Analysis

Roger Shuy (2002) explains different issues about the trademark litigation process. He calls linguistic levels tools for the analysis of trademarks:

Phonetics and Phonology: Phonetics deals with the production, perception, and articulation of speech sounds (Heine & Narrog, 2015). Phonology deals with the organization of speech sounds (Davenport & Hannahs, 2013). These tools analyze similar sound patterns of infringed trademarks including phonetic transcription, phonemic order, syllable count, stress patterns, and pronunciation.

Morphology: Linguistic Morphology is the study of morphemes, words, the internal structure of words, and word-formation processes (Aronoff & Fudeman, 2011). A morpheme refers to the 'smallest meaningful unit of the language'. This level analyzes the beginning and ends of words or stems having derived or inflectional morphemes.

Lexicography: Deals with the study of the lexicon or dictionary (Tarp, 2017). Shuy (2002) asserts that it is important to know about the pronunciation, etymology, and various meanings of trademarks from dictionaries.

Syntax: Deals with sentence structure in a text or document (Van Valin Jr, 2001). However, this level is often taken for granted because sentences are not used in trademarks (Sanderson, 2007).

Semantic and Pragmatic Meaning: Semantic meanings come from the study of meaning of words or phrases regardless of context while pragmatic meanings consider context (Recanatì, 2002).

2.4.2 Butters' Model of Linguistic Analysis

Ronald Butters (2008) proposed a method of analysis comprised of three categories:

The Category of Sight: Considers the appearance of products or trademarks including spelling or formation of words and semiotic features. Butters suggests a formula for identifying the percentage of orthographic 'likelihood' between two trademarks:

The percentage of similarity = (Sum of numbers of shared graphemes / Total number of graphemes in all words) × 100

The Category of Sound: Considers sound patterns including production, perception, articulation, phonemic transcription, and syllable distribution. Formula:

The percentage of similarity = (Sum of numbers of shared phonemes along with stress patterns / Total number of phonemes with stress patterns in all words) × 100

The Category of Meaning: Considers semantic and pragmatic meanings of trademarks.

2.5 Previous Research about Intellectual Property Rights and Trademark Infringement in Pakistan

Mukhtar et al. (2018) gave a detailed understanding of trademark infringement laws and their enforcement in Pakistan under the Paris Convention. They showed that though Pakistan has signed the convention, it is still lacking adequate law enforcement.

Rana (2018) discussed copyright infringement techniques used by advertising agencies in Lahore, Pakistan, giving detailed investigation about different levels of awareness about copyright infringement control.

Khan and Bashir (2019) argued about book piracy in Pakistan as a deliberate form of copyright infringement and utter indifference of authors from their literary works.

Khayyam (n.d.) noticed the protection of trademarks in Pakistan by comparing it with trademark laws of the UK and examining the role of Pakistani agencies like Customs, FIA, DRAP, and IPO in tackling trademark infringement problems.

2.6 Research Gap

Based on studies reviewed, most work on trademark infringement and violation of Intellectual Property Rights has been done in the context of law in Pakistan. Pakistan lacks law enforcement in trademark infringement as many researchers have given suggestions for proper trademark laws enforcement policy. However, there is a need to approach such issues through a forensic linguistics perspective. Therefore, the current study aims to analyze infringement patterns in trademarks through linguistic analysis to give prominence to the field in the trademark litigation process.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This research is qualitative, which means it investigates the experiences of people and benefits people by informing them about the significance of their experiences (Silverman, 2020). Moreover, the study has conducted an ortho-semiotic forensic linguistic analysis of trademarks for the purpose of

investigating the linguistic patterns contributing to the likelihood of confusion. The model of analysis is the product of model triangulation by which relative features of two linguistic models are combined, proposed by Shuy (2002) and Butters (2008).

3.2 Data Collection

For data collection, well-known consumer products in Pakistan and their industries were examined through the internet. The researcher observed that food and cosmetic products in local markets of Pakistan have a noteworthy number of visual similarities with other products. These similarities are found among trademarks possessing similar orthography, visual semiotic features (color, style, and design), sound patterns, and word structure (morphology).

A total number of food products and cosmetic products of multinational as well as local companies which have similar trademarks were sought out. Among all these products, some food and cosmetic products were selected for this research due to time constraints. Selection was based on maximum similarities found among linguistic features of trademarks. Data was collected from publicly available photographs of food and cosmetic products online.

3.3 Data Analysis Procedure

3.3.1 Model Triangulation

For the present research, the researcher followed a method triangulation approach by combining different elements from the above-mentioned models used in forensic linguistic analysis of trademarks.

The Ortho-Semiotic Forensic Linguistic Analysis Model consists of three levels:

Level 1: Orthography and Visual Semiotics

Orthography: Quantification method with formula for determining percentage likelihood

Visual Semiotics: Color, design, and style analysis

Level 2: Phonetics and Phonology

Phonetic transcription

Phonemic order

Syllable stress patterning

Pronunciation similarity/dissimilarity with formula application

Level 3: Morphology

Morphemic study

Quantification method with formula for determining percentage likelihood

3.4 Theoretical Perspective

This research study takes its theoretical background from the work of Olsson (2008) who views Forensic Linguistics as a deep connection between law and linguistic knowledge. He notes a relationship between legal procedures and language because linguistic tools and techniques help during court proceedings. Moreover, forensic linguists consider the forensic text for analysis, defined as "a text that is somehow implicated in a legal or criminal context" (Olsson, 2008, p. 2). In this research, forensic texts are trademarks involved in the criminal act of trademark infringement investigated through forensic linguistic analysis.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

This chapter comprises the data analysis of trademarks of food and cosmetic products. Data is analyzed

in light of the proposed ortho-semiotic forensic linguistic analysis model with three levels:

- a) The level of orthography and visual semiotic language
- b) The level of phonetics and phonology
- c) The level of morphology

4.1 Category (a): Juices and Beverages

4.1.1 Orthographic and Visual Semiotic Analysis

Set-1: Slice vs. Jan

Figure 1: (a) Image of Slice (b) Image of Jan

Orthographic Analysis: The word 'Slice' has five graphemes (s,l,i,c,e) and 'Jan' has three (j,a,n). They share no similar graphemes. Sub-descriptions 'mango' and 'mango drink' share 5 of 5 graphemes in 'mango' and 5 of 10 in 'mango drink'. Shared graphemes: m,a,n,g,o.

Percentage similarity = $10/15 \times 100 = 66\%$

Visual Semiotic Analysis: Both products have the same green color with a leaf at the top, similar illustration of mangoes sliced similarly, and same depiction of mango vines and leaves.

Set-2: Refresh, DayFresh, Fresher

Figure 2: (a) Image of Refresh (b) Image of DayFresh (c) Image of Fresher

Orthographic Analysis: 'Refresh' (7 graphemes), 'DayFresh' (8 graphemes), 'Fresher' (7 graphemes). Shared graphemes (5): f,r,e,s,h.

Percentage similarity = $15/22 \times 100 = 68\%$

Visual Semiotic Analysis: Products 4.2(b) & 4.2(c) have same white color; packaging of 4.2(a) & 4.2(c)

show similar design of mangoes with same yellow color.

Set-3: Sting vs. String

Figure 3: (a) Image of Sting (b) Image of String

Orthographic Analysis: 'Sting' (5 graphemes: s,t,i,n,g), 'String' (6 graphemes: s,t,r,i,n,g). Shared graphemes (5): s,t,i,n,g.

Percentage similarity = $10/11 \times 100 = 90\%$

Visual Semiotic Analysis: Both have same white color; packaging shows similar design of red color with black lines emerging from product name.

Set-4: Mirinda vs. Rango Next

Figure 4: (a) Image of Mirinda (b) Image of Rango Next

Orthographic Analysis: Shared graphemes (3): r,n,a.

Percentage similarity = $7/16 \times 100 = 43\%$

Visual Semiotic Analysis: Orange color of wrappers shows pattern of likelihood; bottles have similar designs, structure, and style.

4.1.2 Phonetic and Phonological Analysis

Table 1: RP Transcriptions of 'mango' and 'mango drink'

Trademark/Word	RP Transcription
mango	/ˈmæŋ ɡəʊ/
mango drink	/ˈmæŋ ɡəʊ /drɪŋk/

Set-1 Percentage similarity = $16/21 \times 100 = 76\%$

Table 2: RP Transcriptions of Refresh, DayFresh, Fresher

Trademark/Word	RP Transcription
Refresh	/rɪ'frɛʃ/
Day Fresh	/deɪ/ /'frɛʃ/
Fresher	/'frɛʃə/

Set-2 Percentage similarity = $15/21 \times 100 = 71\%$

Table 3: RP Transcriptions of Sting and String

Trademark/Word	RP Transcription
Sting	/stɪŋ/
String	/strɪŋ/

Set-3 Percentage similarity = $8/9 \times 100 = 88\%$

Table 4: RP Transcriptions of Mirinda and Rango Next

Trademark/Word	RP Transcription
Mirinda	/mɪ'rændə/
Rango Next	/rʌŋ'gəʊ/ /nɛkst/

Set-4 Percentage similarity = $8/20 \times 100 = 40\%$

4.1.3 Morphological Analysis

Set-1: 'mango' (1 free morpheme), 'mango drink' (2 free morphemes). Shared morpheme: 'mango'.

Percentage similarity = $1/3 \times 100 = 33\%$

Set-2: All trademarks share common free morpheme 'fresh'. Each word has 2 morphemes.

Percentage similarity = $3/6 \times 100 = 50\%$

Set-3: Each word has 1 morpheme ('sting', 'string'). No shared morpheme.

Percentage similarity = **0%**

Set-4: 'Mirinda' (1 free morpheme), 'Rango Next' (2 free morphemes). No shared morpheme.

Percentage similarity = **0%**

4.2 Category (b): Makeup Products

4.2.1 Orthographic and Visual Semiotic Analysis

Set-O: Kylie vs. Kyalinna

Figure 5: (a) Image of Kylie (b) Image of Kyalinna

Orthographic Analysis: 'Kylie' (5 graphemes: k,y,l,i,e), 'Kyalinna' (7 graphemes: k,y,l,i,n,n,a). Shared graphemes (4): k,y,l,i.

Percentage similarity = $8/12 \times 100 = 67\%$

Visual Semiotic Analysis: Design of palettes same (4 colors); both trademarks in upper case; same square shaped palette style; different color (pink vs. transparent).

Set-P: Miss Rose vs. Miis Roos

Figure 6: (a) Image of Miss Rose (b) Image of Miis Roos

Orthographic Analysis: Both have 8 graphemes. Shared graphemes (7 of 8 in Miss Rose, 8 of 8 in Miis Roos).

Percentage similarity = $15/16 \times 100 = 94\%$

Visual Semiotic Analysis: Same red and black packaging; same design of lipsticks; same font style (upper case); similar elongated box shaped packaging.

Set-Q: Huda Beauty, Huxia Beauty, Hedy Beauty, Hunch Beauty, Ihudia Beauty

4.7(a)

4.7(b)

4.7(c)

4.7(d)

4.7(e)

Figure 7: (a-e) Images of five beauty products

Orthographic Analysis: Total graphemes = 55; shared graphemes = 49 (h,u,d,a,i,b,e,a,u,t,y).

Percentage similarity = $49/55 \times 100 = 89\%$

Visual Semiotic Analysis: Same packaging style (lip glosses in boxes); same white and pink color for product names; same font style (upper case); same rectangular transparent bottles with opaque heads.

Set-R: Fit me vs. Fit me

Figure 8: (a) Image of Fit me (b) Image of Fit me

Orthographic Analysis: Both have 5 graphemes (f,i,t,m,e). Shared graphemes = 5 of 5.

Percentage similarity = $10/10 \times 100 = 100\%$

Visual Semiotic Analysis: Same black and skin colors; same transparent bottles with square caps; same design of front wrappers.

Set-S: Topface vs. Sweet Face

Figure 4.9: (a) Image of Topface (b) Image of Sweet Face

Orthographic Analysis: 'Topface' (7 graphemes: t,o,p,f,a,c,e), 'Sweet Face' (9 graphemes: s,w,e,e,t,f,a,c,e). Shared graphemes (5): t,f,a,c,e.

Percentage similarity = $13/16 \times 100 = 81\%$

Visual Semiotic Analysis: Same maroon packaging; same white color for product names.

4.2.2 Phonetic and Phonological Analysis

Table 5: RP Transcriptions of Kylie and Kylinna

Trademark/Word	RP Transcription
Kylie	/'kaɪli/
Kylinna	/'kaɪli:nə/

Set-O Percentage similarity = $11/14 \times 100 = 79\%$

Table 6: RP Transcriptions of Miss Rose and Miis Roos

Trademark/Word	RP Transcription
Miss Rose	/mɪs/ /rəʊz/
Miis Roos	/mɪs/ /ru:s/

Set-P Percentage similarity = $8/13 \times 100 = 62\%$

Table 4.7: RP Transcriptions of Huda Beauty, Huxia Beauty, Hedy Beauty, Hunch Beauty, Ihuidia Beauty

Trademark/Word	RP Transcription
Huda Beauty	/hʊ'də/ /'bjʊ:tɪ/
Huxia Beauty	/hu: ʃɪ:'ɑ:/ /'bjʊ:tɪ/
Hedy Beauty	/'hedi/ /'bjʊ:tɪ/
Hunch Beauty	/hʌntʃ/ /'bjʊ:tɪ/
Ihuidia Beauty	/'hu:diə/ /'bjʊ:tɪ/

Set-Q Percentage similarity = $47/59 \times 100 = 80\%$

Table 4.8: RP Transcriptions of Fit Me and Fit Me

Trademark/Word	RP Transcription
Fit Me	/fɪt/ /mi:/
Fit Me	/fɪt/ /mi:/

Set-R Percentage similarity = $10/10 \times 100 = 100\%$

Table 4.9: RP Transcriptions of Top Face and Sweet Face

Trademark/Word	RP Transcription
Top Face	/tɒp/ /feɪs/
Sweet Face	/swi:t/ /feɪs/

Set-S Percentage similarity = $11/15 \times 100 = 73\%$

4.2.3 Morphological Analysis

Set-O: 'Kylie' (1 morpheme), 'Kylinna' (2 morphemes: Kylie + -nna). Shared morpheme: 'Kylie'.

Percentage similarity = $2/3 \times 100 = 67\%$

Set-P: Both compound words with 2 free morphemes each. Shared morphemes: 'miss' and 'rose'.

Percentage similarity = $4/4 \times 100 = 100\%$

Set-Q: All have 2 morphemes each. Shared morpheme: 'beauty'.

Percentage similarity = $5/10 \times 100 = 50\%$

Set-R: Both have 2 morphemes each ('fit' and 'me').

Percentage similarity = $4/4 \times 100 = 100\%$

Set-S: Both have 2 free morphemes each. Shared morpheme: 'face'.

Percentage similarity = $2/4 \times 100 = 50\%$

5. FINDINGS

5.1 Food Products

Table 5.1: Values of 'Likelihood of Confusion' found among Juices and Beverages

Collected Products	Orthography %	Visual Semiotic (Style/Color/Design)	Phonetics/Phonology %	Morphology %
Slice vs. Jan	66	like/like/like	76	33
Refresh, DayFresh, Fresher	68	like/like/like	71	50
Sting vs. String	90	like/like/like	88	0
Mirinda vs. Rango Next	43	like/like/like	40	0

5.2 Makeup Products

Table 5.2: Values of 'Likelihood of Confusion' found among Cosmetic Makeup Products

Collected Products	Orthography %	Visual Semiotic (Style/Color/Design)	Phonetics/Phonology %	Morphology %
Kylie vs. Kylanina	67	like/unlike/like	79	67
Miss Rose vs. Miis Roos	94	like/like/unlike	62	100
Huda Beauty vs. others	89	like/like/like	80	50
Fit me vs. Fit me	100	like/like/like	100	100
Top Face vs. Sweet Face	81	like/like/unlike	73	50

6. DISCUSSION

This exploratory analysis of trademarks of food and cosmetic products was conducted to find linguistic infringement patterns. These patterns not only involve the linguistic levels of phonetics, phonology, and morphology but also orthography and visual features of semiotics. The model used is ortho-semiotic forensic linguistic analysis, a result of method triangulation combining elements from Butters (2008) and Shuy (2002).

6.1 Ortho-Semiotic Infringement Patterns

Findings identify ortho-semiotic linguistic infringement patterns used by infringers to deceive

customers in Pakistan:

- I. Use of similar font style and color
- II. Use of similar design of packaging
- III. Deceptive use of same sounding letters
- IV. Similarity between sub-descriptions

One possible reason for this infringement may be the use of same visuals (color, style, and design) by infringers (Butters, 2008). In Figures 4.1(a) & 4.1(b), products Slice and Jan share maximum visual similarities. This complete visual likeness is also found in Figures 4.3 and 4.4.

Another possible reason is the use of similar font style and color (Ertekin, Sorescu, & Houston, 2018). Products in Figures 4.3(a) & 4.3(b) have the same font style and color. Results show both words are written in the same manner with white color and block font style.

6.2 Phonetic and Phonological Infringement Patterns

Findings reveal that food and cosmetic products exhibit a great amount of likelihood of confusion caused by phonetic and phonological infringement patterns:

- i. Use of similar phonemic order or positioning in words (Butters, 2008)
- ii. Use of similar first phoneme or first syllable in transcriptions (Sanderson, 2007)
- iii. Use of common word portrayed in phonemic transcriptions (Shuy, 2002)

In products 4.3(a) & 4.3(b), both words Sting and String have the same beginning and ending phonemes (/s/ and /ŋ/). In products 4.5(a) & 4.5(b), both words share the same first phonemes /k/, /y/, and /l/. In products 4.2(a), 4.2(b) & 4.2(c), the word 'fresh' and its phonemic transcription /'frɛʃ/ are shared by all trademarks.

6.3 Morphological Infringement Patterns

Findings reveal the major role of linguistic morphology in finding infringement patterns:

- i. Use of alike morphemic order or placement in words (Butters, 2008)
- ii. Use of same morphemes in beginnings and ends of words (Shuy, 2002)
- iii. Use of common morpheme in alike trademarks (Shuy, 2002)

In products 4.9(a) & 4.9(b), both words share the same ending morpheme 'face'. In products 4.2(a), 4.2(b) & 4.2(c), the morpheme 'fresh' is shared by all trademarks.

7. CONCLUSION

This research has carried out an ortho-semiotic forensic linguistic analysis of trademarks of food and makeup products found in local markets of Pakistan. The data for the current study is not legal cases about trademark infringement in Pakistan but rather a collection of trademarks of alike products which causes likelihood of confusion. This is a forensic linguistic analysis because trademarks are considered forensic texts, as Olsson (2008) says, "a text implicated in legal and criminal context is a forensic text" (p. 2). Based on findings, linguistic levels (orthography, visual semiotics, phonetics, phonology, and morphology) play a primary role in trademark infringement of food and cosmetic products in Pakistan. Findings have revealed that infringers use similar trademarks or words to deceive customers while buying original products. These deceptively similar trademarks cause the 'likelihood of confusion' which affects customers. The percentage infringement ranges from 0% to 100%, denoting gradual use of deceptive language in trademarks. Such increased amount of infringement patterns shows increased dishonesty in society, which is harmful to the public. Poor quality counterfeit food products can cause

health issues, and poor quality cosmetic products can cause skin cancer and other health-related issues. Therefore, based on forensic linguistic knowledge, a fair policy of check and balance should be implemented in Pakistan to decrease the risk of deception to its citizens.

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